

1 **OPINION**

2 **Mojiang mine, RaTG13, miners' disease, and related samples remain essential clues in**
3 **the SARS-CoV-2 origin investigation**

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13 **Keywords: SARS-CoV-2; Mojiang; miners; pneumonia; COVID-19; origin**

14 ***Conflict of interest statement***

15 **The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial**
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17 ***Author contribution statement***

18 MCR and RAB conceived the article. MCR and RAB both wrote the article and approved the final version.

19 ***Keywords***

20 SARS-CoV-2, Mojiang, miners, Pneumonia, COVID-19, origin

21 ***Contribution to the field***

22 We had published an article about the link between the Mojiang mineshaft, RaTG13 and the miners disease. Recently, a paper by
23 Frutos et al 2021 (Frutos et al., 2021) was published which was entitled 'Origin of COVID-19: Dismissing the Mojiang mine theory
24 and the laboratory accident narrative' written to dismiss the Mojiang miners theory. They further say that the miners who
25 worked in a mineshaft in 2012 in Tongguan, Mojiang, Yunnan did not have a SARS-CoV2 infection mentioning our paper (Rahalkar
26 and Bahulikar, 2020). However, their hypothesis is based on the wrong assumption that we had proposed that the miners had
27 COVID-19 or were infected with SARS-CoV-2, which is not the case. In this article, we present our opinion about his article and
28 show that how the clues remain yet to be investigated. In a systematic analyses, we provide an answer to his debunking of the
29 theory and discuss how the analyses of the samples and the mine may provide further answers to this issue. According to a recent
30 opinion article by Paolo Vineis, the case is still open and needs proper investigation, as RaTG13, the next relative of SARS-CoV-2
31 was picked up from the same mine. We also suggest the importance of investigation of the Mojiang mine, miners samples in the
32 SARS-CoV-2 origin investigation.

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35 **Introduction**

36 It has been almost two years since the start of the pandemic, and still, we do not know how
37 COVID-19 started. In July, the Chinese government has rejected the proposal of a second probe
38 by the World Health Organization to investigate the origins of SARS CoV-2
39 <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-china-57926368>. Biden administration ordered a
40 ninety-day intelligence probe, and it remained inconclusive. As demanded by scientists
41 worldwide, there has to be an in-depth investigation into this matter so as to prevent the next
42 pandemics (Bloom et al., 2021). We had published one such vital clue, an article entitled 'Lethal
43 Pneumonia Cases in Mojiang Miners' (2012) and the Mineshaft Could Provide Important Clues
44 to the Origin of SARS-CoV-2' (Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2020). In April 2012, six people
45 cleaned an abandoned bat-infested mineshaft in Tongguan (TG), Mojiang, Yunnan, and
46 suffered from severe pneumonia followed by hospitalization and death in three of them. One
47 of the most expert pulmonologists in China, Dr. Zhong Nanshan had remotely observed the
48 two severe cases (patient 3 and 4) and had diagnosed the pneumonia to be of primary viral
49 origin, with a high probability. Based on a thorough analysis of the medical records, a medical
50 Master's thesis on these six cases was written by Li Xu in 2013. The conclusion of the thesis
51 was: SARS-like bat coronaviruses were suspected to be the causative agents (Xu, 2013). This
52 incident had prompted Shi Zhengli and her group from the WIV to inspect the bat coronaviruses
53 in the mine in 2012, although their paper published in 2016 (Ge et al., 2016) does not mention
54 the miners' pneumonia at all. In a detailed retrospective analysis, the miners' pneumonia was
55 similar to COVID-19 due to the overall similarities (Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2020). We found
56 that the symptoms, blood reports (low lymphocytes, high D-dimers, elevated SAA, etc.), CT
57 scan reports, and the treatments given to treat the pneumonia cases were similar to COVID-19
58 (Xu, 2013; Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2020). After connecting various dots, our paper also
59 highlighted the connection that WIV collected several samples from the same Mojiang mine.

60 One was a SARS-like coronavirus, RaTG13, the closest virus SARS-CoV-2, with 96.2%
61 similarity at the genomic level. RaTG13 had an older name or id BtCoV-Ra4991 (Ge et al.,
62 2016) not revealed by WIV authors in their first paper after the pandemic (Zhou et al., 2020b).
63 After many individual researchers like Rossana Segreto, Dean Bengston revealed that RaTG13
64 and Ra4991 could be the same, Shi Zhengli confirmed this fact in July 2020
65 (www.sciencemag.org, Zhengli Shi Q and A). Also, Shi Zhengli and her group never revealed
66 the points that the nearest neighbor of SARS-CoV-2, RaTG13, was collected from the same
67 Mojiang mine where three of six miners died due to a deadly pneumonia illness until our paper
68 revealing the dual connection was published (Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2020). After the
69 publication of our article, a commentary was published on the same highlighting the
70 importance of this clue (Alex, 2021) and an opinion article (Vineis and Salmaso, 2021).
71 According to the article by Paolo Vineis and colleagues, the case is still open and needs
72 investigation.

73 **Addendum published by WIV: late and contradictions**

74 After the publication of our article (Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2020), an Addendum was
75 published by Shi Zhengli and others (Zhou et al., 2020a), where they declared for the first time
76 that WIV had been sampling the Mojiang mineshaft for a total of three years from 2012-2015.
77 A total of 1322 bat coronavirus samples, including a total of 9 SARS-like coronaviruses, were
78 collected and were brought in the WIV for storage and future study, a fact not disclosed in their
79 prior publications (Ge et al., 2016) (Zhou et al., 2020b). Though WIV revealed that they had
80 collected total of nine SARS-like coronaviruses from the Mojiang mine, of which one was
81 RaTG13, they did not publish the sequence ids or the sequences of these eight isolates in the
82 Addendum (Zhou et al., 2020a). Also, the Addendum did not reveal detailed information of the
83 2012 miners' pneumonia, which was the principal cause behind their three-year hunt for
84 coronaviruses in the Mojiang mine. The Addendum did not refer to the earlier publications

85 associated with the pneumonia cases: the Masters' thesis (Xu, 2013)
86 [https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/6981198-Analysis-of-Six-Patients-With-](https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/6981198-Analysis-of-Six-Patients-With-Unknown-Viruses.html)
87 [Unknown-Viruses.html](https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/6981198-Analysis-of-Six-Patients-With-Unknown-Viruses.html), the Ph.D. thesis (Huang, 2016)
88 [https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/20694207-canping-huang-phd-novel-virus-](https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/20694207-canping-huang-phd-novel-virus-discovery-in-bat-isn-translation)
89 [discovery-in-bat-isn-translation](https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/20694207-canping-huang-phd-novel-virus-discovery-in-bat-isn-translation) and our paper (Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2020).

90 **Rebuttal towards the dismissal of the Mojiang mine theory by Frutos et al. 2021**

91 Recently, a paper by Frutos et al 2021 (Frutos et al., 2021) was published which was entitled
92 'Origin of COVID-19: Dismissing the Mojiang mine theory and the laboratory accident
93 narrative' written to dismiss the Mojiang miners theory. They further say that the miners who
94 worked in a mineshaft in 2012 in Tongguan, Mojiang, Yunnan did not have a SARS-CoV2
95 infection mentioning our paper (Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2020). However, their hypothesis is
96 based on the wrong assumption that we had proposed that the miners had COVID-19 or were
97 infected with SARS-CoV-2, which is not the case. Therefore, the subsequent analysis which
98 follows by Frutos et al 2021 based on this wrong assumption, does not hold much importance.
99 Basically, we have not proposed in our paper (Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2020) that the miners
100 were infected with SARS-CoV-2 and hence had actual CoVID-19. In our paper also we have
101 said that the miners' pneumonia and the disease were overall similar to COVID-19 but not
102 exactly the same. If we consider the gross points and ignore the minute differences, the overall
103 symptom regime is similar to COVID-19, with fever, cough (dry or productive), bilateral
104 pneumonia (interstitial), ARDS (acute respiratory distress syndrome, ground-glass opacities in
105 CT scans and thrombotic complications (Xu, 2013). All of the patients had severe pneumonia,
106 acute respiratory distress syndrome, and most of them needed ventilators (non-invasive and
107 invasive). The deaths occurred due to sudden cardiac arrest (patient 1, within ten days) or
108 respiratory failure (patient 2 and 3). A similar death scenario is present in the majority of the
109 COVID-19 patients. The minor differences between the symptoms and CT scans of the miners

110 and COVID-19, as pointed out by Frutos et al. 2021 could be due to the fact that the virus was
111 not SARS-CoV-2. We had consulted a reputed radiologist for his opinion about the CT scans
112 and radiology analysis in the Master's Thesis by Li Xu 2013. According to him, the scans of
113 patients 2, 3, and 4 were most typical of the scans found in COVID-19. The significant
114 observations regarding the CT scans were: 'Most of the cases have following findings. 1.
115 Diffuse ground-glass opacities. 2. Peripheral subpleural ground-glass opacities. 3. Some areas
116 of peripheral consolidation. These findings are consistent with what we see nowadays in
117 Covid. Consolidation can be due to superadded infection in these patients, bacterial fungal
118 etc.'

119 Also, secondary bacterial and fungal infections can cause variation within patients, such as
120 mucus color and minor level differences in CT scans stated by Frutos et al 2021. Secondary
121 infections have also been reported in COVID-19 (Lai et al., 2020). Not all thrombotic
122 complications necessarily mean COVID-19, as pointed out by Frutos et al. 2021, but blood
123 clots and thrombosis are significantly common in most COVID-19 patients. The remarkably
124 high D-dimers values indicative of the blood clots are not typically found in SARS, influenza,
125 or other illnesses. As noted by our study and Frutos et al. 2021, almost all the patients showed
126 high D-dimers. In conclusion, we had said in our original paper that a virus highly similar to
127 SARS-CoV-2 or RaTG13 could have infected the miners, and this is based on the fact that the
128 SARS-like illness the miners experienced was more like COVID-19 and not like SARS1. In
129 the case of SARS1, the pneumonia is unilateral in 50% of cases (Hosseiny et al., 2020). Also,
130 the virus found in the mine, RaTG13, was more related to SARS-CoV-2 and not SARS1.

131 **Positive IgG Ab in miners as documented by Canping Huang and other controversies:**

132 Also, Frutos et al. have not mentioned the positive IgG antibody tests reported in the 4/4
133 patients, documented by Huang Canping in 2016 (Huang, 2016), translation:

134 [https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/20694207-canping-huang-phd-novel-virus-](https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/20694207-canping-huang-phd-novel-virus-discovery-in-bat-isn-translation)
135 [discovery-in-bat-isn-translation.](https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/20694207-canping-huang-phd-novel-virus-discovery-in-bat-isn-translation) Huang Canping was a student of George Gao, CCDCP
136 director, China, who also had said in a recent interview with France2 that the miners had IgG
137 antibodies for SARS-like viruses. Also, Frutos 2021 (Frutos et al., 2021) mentioned the
138 opinion of a consulting doctor saying that the miners had a fungal infection, but no supportive
139 evidence is provided to the diagnosis. Also, the study fails to quote the diagnosis by Dr. Zhong
140 Nanshan, one of the most prominent pulmonologists in China. Dr. Nanshan suggested that the
141 two miners admitted (patients 3 and 4) probably had primary interstitial viral pneumonia and
142 secondary infection in the form of invasive pulmonary aspergillosis. Being the most prominent
143 doctor during SARS, his diagnosis is one of the utmost important opinions in this case. He had
144 asked to do a throat swab and a SARS-Ab test. He had also asked to investigate which types of
145 horseshoe bats were present in the mine, indicating that he also suspected it to be a SARS-like
146 infection. We cannot also forget the fact that the miners' disease was the reason why Shi
147 Zhengli and her colleagues were asked to visit the mine and collect samples and analyze for
148 coronaviruses. Though Shi did not mention this in the Ge 2016 paper, in an Addendum to her
149 original article Shi Zhengli and her co-workers, have clearly stated that they had suspected an
150 unknown virus to be the culprit in the miners and therefore had sampled the mine for three
151 years (2012-2015). These facts are not mentioned in the Frutos (Frutos et al., 2021) paper.
152 Hence, the connection of RaTG13 with the Mojiang mine, where three miners died due to
153 pneumonia caused by a SARS-like virus, does not go away. Nor does the fact that WIV was
154 instrumental in collecting the SARS-like coronaviruses from the same mine, sequencing the
155 closest relatives (RaTG13 and eight more). Our theory, as evident from our publication and the
156 commentary published on our paper (Alex, 2021), hypothesizes that the miners could have
157 been a spill-over infection from the horseshoe bats as they were directly exposed to the bat
158 guano they were sweeping and cleaning.

159 **Mojiang Mine, inaccessible and closed for reporters and researchers**

160 Access to the Mojiang mine, at the center of everyone's attention, has been completely denied
161 by China. Reporters from the Associated Press, BBC, France2, WSJ, and many other media
162 groups could not reach the area because of roadblocks and secret police in 2020 and 2021. The
163 Wall Street Journal reported that one of its reporters was detained by police, and the photo was
164 deleted. In December 2020, Associated Press had reported China was keeping the Mojiang
165 mine off-limits to researchers and journalists. A bat research team that visited recently had their
166 samples confiscated, as per the AP news report.

167 Shi Zhengli mentioned in her Scientific American interview (Qiu, 2020) that the mine was
168 promptly closed (most probably after the 2012 incident for outsiders). However, the last
169 reported samplings are from the researchers of China CDC, which sampled in October 2014,
170 and WIV in 2015 (Huang, 2016; Zhou et al., 2020a). There are no apparent records of sampling
171 after 2015 in the Mojiang mine or details about which samples were brought from the mine.

172 **Conclusion and future aspects:**

173 1. The Mojiang mine is an abandoned mine in Yunnan, Southern China, from which RaTG13,
174 one of the nearest neighbors of SARS-CoV-2 was collected by WIV. WIV is the most premium
175 institute located in Wuhan, working extensively on coronaviruses, and has 22,000 samples
176 collected.

177 2. The same mine in Mojiang was the place where six people went to clean the bat guano, fell
178 ill with severe pneumonia, and three of them died, 2012. The miners suffered from severe
179 respiratory distress, and some had thrombotic complications, all reasonably similar to that of
180 COVID-19.

181 3. We did not say in our earlier paper (Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2020) that the miners had
182 COVID-19, and therefore the assumption of (Frutos et al., 2021) is wrong.

183 4. WIV visited the mines and brought 1322 samples from the mine in their visits from 2012-
184 2015 and analyzed serum samples from the miners. Recently they reported that they performed
185 certain tests on these samples, which indicates that they have the samples from the miners since
186 2012.

187 5. Our suggestion is that all the samples from the miners (serum samples, throat swabs, etc.)
188 should be given to a third party international research laboratory, and metagenomic data from
189 all these samples would clarify the situation, as suggested by Alex Speciale, in a commentary
190 on our paper (Alex, 2021).

191 6. Also, all the information in the databases and computers about the samples and sequencing
192 done on the Mojiang mine samples and the miners samples should be opened to the
193 international community for scrutiny.

194 7. Any kind of experiments using RaTG13 or other viruses samples collected from the mine
195 should be revealed.

196 8. The Mojiang mine should be opened to international researchers for sampling and journalists
197 for the history of the mine after 2012-2020.

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